

Synthesis, characterization, and antitumor evaluation of a kaempferol–cobalt(II) complex targeting *TMPRSS2* gene in lung cancer cells

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Abstract

Background: Transmembrane serine protease 2 (*TMPRSS2*) has been distinguished as a tumor suppressor in lung adenocarcinoma, and its reduced expression has been associated with disease progression.

Aim: To estimate the effects of a kaempferol–metal complex on lung cancer cells and assess its influence on *TMPRSS2* gene expression in comparison with standard kaempferol.

Materials and methods: A kaempferol–cobalt(II) complex was synthesized, and the cytotoxicity of the complex against A549 lung cancer cells was estimated using an MTT assay. The mRNA expression of the *TMPRSS2* gene was assessed using quantitative real-time PCR analysis.

Results: A molecular docking study revealed that the kaempferol–cobalt(II) complex displays better binding affinity toward *TMPRSS2* compared with free kaempferol and selective cytotoxicity, with an IC_{50} value of 58.21 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Quantitative real-time PCR analysis revealed that treatment with the kaempferol–cobalt(II) complex significantly elevated *TMPRSS2* gene expression (7.3-fold).

Conclusion: Cobalt(II) complexation may be considered a promising candidate for further anticancer investigation.

Keywords

A549 cells, docking study, kaempferol–Co(II) complex, *TMPRSS2* gene

Introduction

One of the leading causes of death is lung cancer. Despite the progress in cancer treatment over the past few decades, the five-year survival average is only 19% (Siegel et al. 2020). Lung adenocarcinoma (LUAD), a subtype of non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), accounts for more than 40% of all lung cancers. EGFR and KRAS are

heterogenic mutations that play a role in the biological variation of LUAD patients, which in turn plays a role in treating them more effectively. Cancer immunotherapy, which uses antibodies such as anti-CTLA4 and anti-PD1, has proven effective in treating LUAD and has significantly improved chemotherapy. This has prompted further exploration of the relationship between tumor

biomarkers and immune cells (Xiao et al. 2022). Transmembrane serine protease 2 (*TMPRSS2*) is generally expressed in prostate gland epithelial cells and is also classified as a type II transmembrane serine protease (TTSP) (Lin et al. 1999). Many studies have demonstrated a connection between different types of cancer and *TMPRSS2*, with its role varying depending on the cancer type. This role involves factors such as gene fusion and immune cell infiltration. Prostate cancer has received the most documented evidence of this role, as the fusion of the *TMPRSS2* gene with *ERG* is a common occurrence. However, in breast and lung cancers, it is a positive biomarker in some immune cells and a weak biomarker in others. This depends on the cancer immune environment (Giunchi et al. 2020). Several oncogenic pathways in LUAD are upregulated by the downregulation of the *TMPRSS2* gene, including cell cycle, p53, mismatch repair, and ECM signaling. Increased cancer cell proliferation, stem cell growth, genomic instability, and ITH in LUAD are also associated with downregulation of the *TMPRSS2* gene (Liu et al. 2024). Low expression of *TMPRSS2* is linked with increased DNA methylation, and this may affect immune cell infiltration and metabolism, suggesting that *TMPRSS2* can serve as a diagnostic biomarker or therapeutic target (Liu et al. 2022). One of the most promising natural plant components for anticancer and antiviral activity is flavonoids (Pyo et al. 2024). Numerous studies have confirmed the role of flavonoids in the prevention and treatment of lung cancer, highlighting some of their complex molecular mechanisms of action and potential targets. These include important mechanisms covering the modification of enzymes that metabolize carcinogenic substances, specific cell-cycle arrest and apoptosis activation, modulation of cell-signaling pathways, and inhibition of key transcription factor activators (Zanoaga et al. 2019).

Flavonoid–mineral complexes have been reported to possess diverse biopharmaceutical and medicinal properties, exhibiting many biological characteristics, such as anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antiviral, anti-allergic, and cytotoxic activity and anticarcinogenic properties

(Mohammed Ali Mohsen et al. 2024). Studies show evidence that metal flavonoid complexes have potent therapeutic characteristics against different classes of cancer cells (Adhikari et al. 2024; Mihajlović et al. 2025). The importance of flavonoids as chelated agents plays an important role in their ability to coordinate hydroxyl groups and carbonyl groups to reduce metal complexes (Khater et al. 2019). Atoms that have one or more pairs of free electrons, such as nitrogen, oxygen, phosphorus, and sulfur, can act as donors in flavonoid constructions, which in turn result in stable metal complexes. The role of mineral flavonoids has recently emerged in the expansion of new drugs, because some current anticancer treatments are insufficient in achieving adequate results in treating cancer (Shi and Zhang 2019). In addition, *TMPRSS2* was considered a future therapeutic target. The present study aimed to estimate the effects of the kaempferol–metal complex on lung cancer cells and to assess its influence on protease gene expression in comparison with standard kaempferol.

Materials and methods

Chemical synthesis of kaempferol–Co(II) complex

To a solution of kaempferol (3.5 mmol, 1 g) in methanol (30 mL), a solution of $\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1.75 mmol, 0.2 g) was added. NaOH (3.5 mmol, 0.14 g) was added dropwise. The combination was refluxed for 4 h at 60 °C. The progress of the reaction was followed by TLC using diethyl ether:acetic acid:toluene (6:4:1). Under reduced pressure, the solvent was evaporated. The residue was re-dissolved in distilled water, and the filtrate was left to dry overnight. The formed precipitate was recrystallized from methanol. Scheme 1. Kaempferol–Co(II) complex $[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$: yield (68%) as a dark brown powder, m.p. 300 °C d. Rf value = 0.2. FT-IR in KBr disc ($\nu = \text{cm}^{-1}$): 3402 (O–H) broad peak, 1598.99 (C = O), and 837.11 and 800 cm^{-1} (Co–O). ESI-MS, (M^+): m/z: 661.35 (Suppl. materials 1, 2).

Scheme 1. Chemical synthesis of kaempferol–Co(II) complex.

Molecular docking study

The current study used computer-based methods to resolve the tested molecules' potential binding to the transmembrane protease serine 2 (*TMPRSS2*) active site. The protein (*TMPRSS2*) and the newly synthesized kaempferol–Co(II) complex were optimized using the MMFF94 force field, and the Protein Data Bank (PDB) provided the protein structure (Protein ID: 7MEQ). Molecular docking was then performed, generating 20 potential orientations. The pose with the best affinity was selected based on root mean square deviation (RMSD) values and affinity scores.

Cytotoxicity evaluation

The MTT cytotoxic assay was applied to evaluate the cytotoxicity (van de Loosdrecht et al. 1994). Cells were cultured in RPMI-1640 (provided with 1% sodium bicarbonate, 10% FBS, 10³ IU penicillin, and 0.001 g streptomycin) in 96-well plates at a density of 1 × 10⁴ cells/mL (100 µL/well). In a humidified atmosphere at 37 °C and a 5% CO₂ incubator (Gallenkamp, England), the cells were incubated. After one day of seeding, cells were processed with medium supplied with 25, 50, 100, 200, and 400 µg/mL concentrations of kaempferol alone or kaempferol–Co(II) complex and incubated for 24 h. After 24 h, PBS was used to wash the cells, and they were detached with trypsin-EDTA and suspended completely in fresh medium. Each concentration was used in three replicates. After treatment, 10 µL of MTT solution [3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide] was added to each well, and cells were further incubated in 5% CO₂ for 4 h at 37 °C. Media were discarded, and to dissolve formazan crystals, 100 µL of solubilization solution was added. The absorbance was recorded at 575 nm by an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) reader (ThermoFisher, Japan). To determine the selective cytotoxicity, the IC₅₀ concentration was calculated for kaempferol alone or the kaempferol–Co(II) complex against the cancer cell line A549 compared with the normal HDFn cell line.

Total RNA extraction and reverse transcription

According to the manufacturer's recommendations, total RNA was isolated with the Total RNA Mini Kit (Blood/Cultured Cell) (Geneaid) from untreated control cells and A549 cells treated with IC₅₀ kaempferol–Co(II) complex and kaempferol alone. To guarantee the highest quality of RNA, a Nanodrop device was employed prior to real-time PCR. The M-MLV reverse transcriptase kit (Sigma) was used for cDNA synthesis from 2 µg RNA, according to the manufacturer's guide.

Gene expression analysis

The *TMPRSS2* gene expression was estimated by quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR). A set of primers was used for amplification of the *TMPRSS2*

gene (Park and Gallagher 2017), using the PowerUp SYBR Green Master Mix, depending on the manufacturer's information. All experiments were conducted three times. The change in expression of the *TMPRSS2* gene was compared to the reference gene β-actin, and the mRNA expression was calculated using the following formula: Relative quantification (RQ) = 2^{-ΔΔCt}.

Statistical analyses

GraphPad Prism software (version 9.4) was used to analyze the data, and the findings were expressed as mean ± standard deviation (SD). One-way analyses of variance (ANOVA) and Duncan's post hoc test were utilized to evaluate significant differences between all groups. A *p*-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results and discussion

Chemical synthesis and characterization

Kaempferol, the natural flavonoid compound, exhibits relatively low solubility in water due to its chemical structure (Herrera et al. 2025). The compound's aromatic rings and hydroxyl groups contribute to its polarity, but the overall hydrophobic character of the molecule limits its ability to dissolve in aqueous solutions. This poor water solubility can pose challenges in formulating kaempferol-based products and delivering the compound effectively in biological systems (Li et al. 2021). Chemical synthesis of the new complex involved the reaction of kaempferol with cobalt chloride hexahydrate (CoCl₂·6H₂O) in methanol (2:1). A solution of NaOH was used to facilitate the deprotonation of the hydroxyl group and coordination bond formation. After completing the reaction, the residue was re-dissolved in water to remove the non-reactive materials, dried, and recrystallized from methanol. Kaempferol solubility increases when complexed with cobalt(II) due to several structural and physicochemical changes. Primarily, the overall polarity of the molecule is enhanced after metal complex formation, leading to better interaction with polar solvents such as water and ethanol. In addition, the combination of kaempferol with metal disrupts the kaempferol hydrogen bonds within the kaempferol molecule, thus allowing hydroxyl groups to react with solvents. This process often leads to a transition from a crystalline to an amorphous structure, which exhibits higher solubility due to its disordered molecular arrangement and higher free energy (Syed et al. 2023). These combined effects result in a significant improvement in solubility (Jayed et al. 2025).

In the FT-IR spectrum of kaempferol, the distinct peaks are related to hydroxyl and carbonyl groups, which appear at ν (3410.15 and 1660.71) cm⁻¹, respectively (Kumar et al. 2024). In the FT-IR spectrum of the kaempferol–Co(II) complex, a broad peak at ν (3402.4) cm⁻¹ was associated with the stretching vibration of hydroxyl groups, and the carbonyl group appeared at ν (1598.99) cm⁻¹. The peaks

at ν (837.11 and 800) cm^{-1} are assigned to Co–O coordinated bonds. The shifting of peaks in the complex to lower frequencies indicates that both OH and C = O groups are involved in complex synthesis (Mutlu Gençkal et al. 2020). The mass spectrometry analysis (ESI-MS) was used to prove the chemical structure of the newly synthesized complex. The significant ion peaks are shown in Table 1. The results suggested that kaempferol's 3-OH and 4-oxo interacted with Co(II) with the loss of a hydrogen atom in addition to coordinating with a water molecule. The main ions obtained were m/z : 661.35, 643.90, 625.30, 378.40, 360.70, and 342.05. These data estimated that two molecules of kaempferol and one atom of Co(II) contributed to complex synthesis. The proposed structure of the complex was compatible with these results.

Table 1. The main ion peaks of the kaempferol–Co(II) complex using ESI-MS analysis.

Peak	Interpretation
661.35	M^+
643.90	$[\text{Co}(\text{Kam})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}] - \text{H}_2\text{O}$
625.30	$[\text{Co}(\text{Kam})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}] - 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$
378.40	$[\text{Co}(\text{Kam})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}] - \text{Kam}$
360.70	$[\text{Co}(\text{Kam})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}] - (\text{Kam} + \text{H}_2\text{O})$
342.05	$[\text{Co}(\text{Kam})_2, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}] - (\text{Kam} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O})$

Molecular docking study

The molecular docking simulation was performed to evaluate the potential interaction of the kaempferol–Co(II) complex with the transmembrane protease serine 2 (*TMPSR2*), which is an important agent in the progression and development of prostate cancer (Yang et al. 2024). The binding model of the tested compound and nafamostat (original ligand of Protein ID: 7MEQ) is illustrated in Fig. 1. According to the data illustrated in

Table 2, nafamostat, the co-crystallized ligand of 7MEQ (*TMPSR2*), shows a binding energy of -4.7058 kcal/mol with two hydrogen bonds between the guanidine group and Asp435 and Gly464. While the kaempferol complex derivative showed better affinity toward the target protein with a binding energy of -5.4206 kcal/mol, additionally, it formed three hydrogen bonds between phenolic hydroxyl groups and Val280, Gly391, and Ser460.

Table 2. The binding affinity (kcal/mol) of the kaempferol–Co(II) complex with the type of interaction against 7MEQ.

Protein	Compound	S Kcal/mol	RMSD	Interaction with 7MEQ	
				H.B	π
Protease2: ID 7MEQ	Kaempferol-Co(II) complex	-5.4206	1.6988	3	-
	Nafamostat	-4.7058	1.4647	2	-

S: affinity score; RMSD: root mean square deviation.

Cytotoxic activity of the kaempferol-Co(II) complex

MTT assays were employed to assess the impact of 24 h exposure to kaempferol alone and the kaempferol–Co(II) complex on the A549 cell line's vitality. Fig. 2A, B demonstrates that both kaempferol and the kaempferol–Co(II) complex exhibited minimal cytotoxic effects on normal HDFn cells, in contrast to their significantly higher cytotoxicity against cancer cells, suggesting potential selectivity toward malignant cells. The cancer cells' survival rate falls as the kaempferol–Co(II) complex concentration rises. Thus, it may be said that the kaempferol–Co(II) complex can eliminate cancer cells without endangering healthy cells.

Cytotoxicity assays are widely used to screen cytotoxic compounds. Metal flavonoid complexes recently played a distinguished role in new drug development

Figure 1. 2D and 3D binding model of **A.** The kaempferol–Co(II) complex and **B.** Nafamostat inside the active pocket of 7MEQ.

Figure 2. Cell viability of human cancer cell lines. A. Cell viability (%) of human lung carcinoma (A549) treated with kaempferol compared with the normal human dermal fibroblasts (HdFn); B. A549 cell viability (%) treated with kaempferol-Co(II) complex. Statistical analysis was applied with one-way ANOVA and Duncan's subtest.

because some current anticancer treatments are unable to provide sufficient results in cancer treatment (Zan-gade et al. 2024). The current findings demonstrated a dose-dependent cytotoxic effect of kaempferol and the kaempferol-Co(II) complex on A549 with IC₅₀ values of 118.0 µg/mL and 58.21 µg/mL, respectively, compared with significantly lower cytotoxicity in HdFn cells, SI = 1.11 for kaempferol compared to SI = 2.03 for the complex. The obtained selective cytotoxicity indicates that the kaempferol-Co(II) complex may have selective toxicity against cancer cells, a key feature of a promising anticancer candidate. The results of the current study are compatible with those of the Wang et al. 2014 study (Wang et al. 2014), which demonstrated improved cytotoxicity of the kaempferol Cu(II) and Zn(II) complex against breast cancer cells after 24 h of exposure to the complex compared to free kaempferol. Flavonoid metal complexes play a significant role in fighting cancer cells through several mechanisms, most notably stimulating programmed cell death, increasing oxidative stress, and halting the cell cycle, targeting cancer cells more effectively than free flavonoids. By generating reactive oxygen species (ROS), modifying DNA, and interfering with topoisomerase I and II, these compounds also demonstrate a greater ability to block proliferation of cancer cells, invasion, and spread (Tumilaar et al. 2024).

Evaluation of the kaempferol-Co(II) complex on *TMPRSS2* gene expression

This study investigates the impact of the kaempferol-Co(II) complex on lung cancer by examining its effect pattern on *TMPRSS2* gene expression in human lung cell lines that have been treated with the IC₅₀ concentration (58.21 µg/mL) of the kaempferol-Co(II) complex compared with the IC₅₀ concentration (118.0 µg/mL) of kaempferol alone. The expression of the *TMPRSS2* gene at 24 h after treatment with the kaempferol-Co(II) complex showed a significant increase of 7.3 (*p*-value < 0.05), while the *TMPRSS2* gene showed no significant expression compared to the β-actin gene (*p*-value < 0.01) (Fig. 3).

Recent studies demonstrate the crucial role of the *TMPRSS2* gene in facilitating the entry of coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) into alveolar cells and the presence of

Figure 3. Expression rate of *TMPRSS2* gene at 24 h treatment. ns: Non-significant, ***p* < 0.01.

TMPRSS2 expression in lung tissue. This discovery may have significant therapeutic implications (Giunchi et al. 2020). The objective of the current study is to test whether the prepared kaempferol complex had an effect on the gene expression of the protease gene in lung cancer cells, after several recent studies confirmed its reduced expression in lung cancer cells compared to healthy lung tissue, as well as its correlation with cancer patient survival rates (Kong et al. 2020). The result shown in Fig. 3 confirms that the prepared kaempferol-Co(II) complex can increase gene expression by a factor of 7.3 compared to free kaempferol, and this complex may be a promising compound or a synergistic compound with cancer drugs. This conclusion is based on the results of the Liu et al. (2024) study, which confirmed that downregulation of *TMPRSS2* is associated with increased proliferation, tumor progression, and reduced survival rates for LUAD patients due to genomic instability.

Many studies demonstrated the effect of kaempferol on lung cancer by different mechanisms, including induction of apoptosis and regulation of key signaling pathways such as nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor 2 (NRF2) (Wang et al. 2023). NRF2 has been displayed to suppress the expression of *TMPRSS2* through binding to its promoter region. In addition, NRF2

upregulates the expression of AT2R and ACE2, contributing to lung protection against infection (Khan et al. 2021). Kaempferol manifests a dual, context-dependent effect on the NRF2 pathway. In normal tissue, kaempferol may activate NRF2 to protect against oxidative stress and inflammation, whereas in cancer cells it can inhibit the activity of NRF2, thereby enhancing cellular sensitivity to treatment. This effect is thought to occur by direct interaction with its negative regulator protein, Keap1, which is a key regulator of NRF2.

In lung cancer, the activation of NRF2 often promotes tumor cell survival, metabolic adaptation, and resistance to therapy (Kaur et al. 2024; Verza et al. 2025). Accordingly, therapeutic strategies that inhibit NRF2 using natural products such as flavonoids, in combination with stress inducers such as cobalt chloride (CoCl₂), aim to disrupt antioxidant defenses and induce cancer cell death via ferroptosis or apoptosis. CoCl₂ acts as a hypoxia and oxidative stress mimetic, promoting NRF2-dependent pro-survival signaling, which can then be counteracted by NRF2 inhibitory flavonoids. This prepared kaempferol-Co(II) complex creates a synergistic antitumor effect through overwhelming the cancer cell antioxidant system and overcoming therapeutic resistance (Hammad et al. 2019).

Conclusion

A kaempferol-Co(II) complex was successfully synthesized and characterized, and its cytotoxicity was estimated against the A549 lung cell line. The complex showed good but selective cytotoxicity toward A549 lung cancer cells compared with free kaempferol. Molecular docking suggested a favorable interaction with the *TMPRSS2* protein, and gene expression analysis demonstrated a significant upregulation of *TMPRSS2* in treated cancer cells, highlighting the role of *TMPRSS2* as a tumor suppressor in LUAD. Although further mechanistic and *in vivo* studies are required, the kaempferol-Co(II) complex represents a promising lead for lung cancer-focused medicinal chemistry investigations.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

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Author contributions

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

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Supplementary material 1

Supplementary image 1

Authors: Zainab Tuama Al-Dallee, Hiba Najeh Alsaad, Sabaa Ali Mohammed Al-Fadal

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Supplementary material 2

Supplementary image 2

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